

SHERPA
Rural Science-Society-Policy
Interfaces

MAP Position Paper

DIGITALISATION IN RURAL AREAS

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Find out more about the Multi-Actor Platform of the Portuguese Central region,
<https://rural-interfaces.eu/maps/portugal-centro/>

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Summary and key messages

Digital transformation is an economy-wide challenge. It requires to strengthen connectivity and digital skills that go beyond the agricultural sector, and because of that, there are other instruments than the Common Agricultural Policy to address it. The Digitalisation Strategy intends to address five specific objectives:

- OB 1: To promote technology transfer, advice, extension, knowledge sharing
- OB 2: To improve digital skills
- OB 3: Connectivity
- OB 4: Improving the environment for digitisation
- OB 5: To transform data into information to support decision-making

This third cycle of MAP RURAL_PT, given the chosen theme, took the decision to focus on a single region in Central Portugal, Fundão. The choice of this municipality was based on the whole local innovation and investment strategy implemented since 2013, and with a huge success. All the work developed with the Multi-Actor Platform (MAP) members, connected to policy, science, and society, allowed the identification of the main needs of the region, in terms of digitalisation, the identification of the main actions already implemented in the field, as well as the main knowledge gaps. However, given the sector of activity of the members involved, the analysis carried out had a greater focus on the agricultural sector of the region and the associated digital transition challenges.

The digital transformation of agriculture, with the integration of new digital technologies, is fundamental to support the agricultural sector to address the strong challenges of digitisation, responding to the growing demand for food, without compromising sustainability in terms of environment, climate and resources. This means producing more with less, while having a positive impact on the quality of life of farmers, and thus contributing to attracting new generations to this sector.

In the region of Fundão, this promotion by digitalisation has been strategically implemented, through different plans, actions and local initiatives, such as: i) Strategic Plan for Innovation of the Municipality of Fundão; ii) Creation of the Living Lab Cova da Beira; iii) Creation of Digital Innovation Hubs (DIH4Sm@rtRegions; PT.DIGMAKING.IH; EDIH-F4S); iv) Des Agro 4.0 Project, co-financed by FEDER programme; v) Agrotech IoT Centre; vi) Incubator A Praça; vii) EU SOU DIGITAL - Digital Training Programme for Adults; viii) Agricultural Innovation Fair; ix) AgroTech Challenge.

All the work developed in the scope of this MAP has shown that there is still much work to be done regionally to improve the context for digitalisation, mainly related to the agricultural sector. Action that is more significant is needed at multiple levels, ranging from the free availability of aggregated information in the Public Administration, the speed of the decision-making process of investment support, the reduction of administrative burden, the adoption of new support models more adjusted to the reality and business dynamics (the acquisition of specialised services appears as an alternative to purchasing equipment). This way is intended to promote a set of incentives and raise awareness for their adoption by the whole sector, as well as to support to group investments and commitments to collect and share data.

It is important to continue to work regionally to make a decisive contribution to promote digitalisation and introduce the use of new technologies and their development, and maximise their impact for the benefit of the agricultural sector, rural areas, environmental preservation, and public administration. New digital technologies can revolutionise agriculture in its practices, food circuits, production factors or in administration.

1. Introduction

Digitalisation is a reality and a necessity nowadays, materialised in a society and economy increasingly based on science, technological development, and innovation. In this sense, there has been a significant investment to promote a new digital era at European level.

Portugal, aiming to catch up with Europe in the digital domain, has been following the European path through the promotion of several initiatives, programs, plans and strategies. An example is the XXII Government's Programme, which defines the digital transition as a strategic priority and fundamental vector for the country's economic growth. In parallel, it is essential to promote the alignment of national digital priorities with European Union policies, regulatory frameworks, and funding sources in order to maximise the impact of the results.

Digital transition should be seen as an engine for the transformation of the country, as well for the creation of more and better jobs, the internationalisation of companies and the modernisation of the State and society in general. To this end, it is essential to act at the level of people, companies and the State, as structural dimensions of digital transition, and create the conditions for all to address their challenges (Action Plan for the Digital Transition of Portugal, 2020).

The new Strategic Plans for the Common Agricultural Policy 2023-2027 (SPCAP) have three main objectives related to: i) securing food supply; ii) contributing to the follow-up of the environmental and climate objectives of the European Union; iii) socio-economic development of rural territories. Additionally, the SPCAP also has a transversal objective of "modernising the sector by promoting and sharing knowledge, innovation and digitalisation in agricultural and rural areas and promoting their adoption". Following this line of action, Portugal developed its Strategy based on five main objectives: 1) promoting technology transfer, advice, extension, and knowledge sharing; 2) improving digital skills; 3) connectivity; 4) improving the context for digitalisation; 5) transformation of data into information to support decision-making.

MAP RURAL_PT focused on the study of a region of the country, the municipality of Fundão. This municipality committed to the digital transition, through various actions, initiatives, plans and programs. More specifically, this municipality has been investing, over the past few years, in a strategy to attract investment, create jobs and foster innovation to promote the diversification of the local economy and a socio-economic development adapted to the dynamics of the current economy marked by globalisation and digitalisation.

To continue the work developed so far, the MAP RURAL_PT promoted the collaboration and joint work of a diverse and multidisciplinary group of local actors, represented by entities linked to policy, society and science. This collaboration aim at assessing the region according to the thematic of digitalisation, with respect to: (i) local needs; (ii) examples of policy interventions already in place; (iii) examples of actions undertaken by local actors; (iv) recommended policy interventions at local, regional and national level and, how can the European Union support these interventions; (v) what are the knowledge gaps and what new research will be needed.

2. Current situation based on background research and evidence

When it comes to digitalisation and technology, large urban centres are the first choice on the list as they are main concentration centres of companies working in these fields. This is one of the reasons that leads to a greater desertification in rural areas, in addition to the fact that rural areas generally also present less attractive infrastructures. The mission of betting on the digital transition, successfully assumed by Fundão, was born to counteract the desertification trend. Their experience has shown that it is possible to attract companies of excellence, with qualified people, in the area of information technologies, to rural areas.

Following this chapter, examples of plans, actions and initiatives implemented in Fundão to promote digitalisation in the region will be presented.

2.1. Strategic Plan for Innovation of the Municipality of Fundão

The [Strategic Plan for Innovation of the Municipality of Fundão](#), implemented in this region since 2013, was developed with to reverse the process of degradation of the economic fabric of the municipality and demographic ageing through the implementation of innovative and differentiating solutions.

This plan allows the creation of structural conditions and services dedicated to entrepreneurship and private initiative, promoting a culture open to the exterior, of applied knowledge and profitability of human capital. Human capital, with emphasis on talent retention and attraction, as well as digital literacy for youth and adults, is one of the focal points of this plan. In terms of digital literacy, it is worth mentioning the introduction of computer programming in a universal way: in all public education in the municipality of Fundão, for all young people from six years old and in all schools. Fundão was a pioneer in this initiative.

This strategic plan reinforces the importance of local infrastructures, to promote the reception of new businesses, the importance of incentives and support to investors and entrepreneurs and the importance of promoting the municipality as a destination for innovation and investment.

The concept of innovation, linked to this region, does not consist only in technological factors, but is intended to be applied to a diversity of domains, and implies the construction of synergies and convergence platforms that promote opportunities for success, such as Living Labs. The creation of these spaces, physical or digital, in the region of Fundão is essentially related to the opportunity to create territorial cooperation networks, a fundamental factor to spread innovative and integrated logics that provide a dynamic flow.

2.2. Living Lab Cova da Beira (LLCB)

According to the [Strategic Plan for Innovation of the Municipality of Fundão](#), the Living Lab Cova da Beira (LLCB) allowed to start a process of cooperative work between various stakeholders based on a philosophy of openness, dialogue and empowerment of the communities. The LLCB paid a special attention to two central topics: i) attraction of investment; ii) creation of a favourable environment for the development of companies and their potential to create wealth and employment. Through the LLCB, a set of valences were developed that comprise an open ecosystem where different local agents move, different areas of knowledge and services involved in the whole innovation process.

2.3. Digital Innovation Hubs (DIH)

According to the Municipality of Fundão (CMF), the region is part of the consortium for the creation of a Digital Innovation Hubs (DIH), with the aim of promoting new collaborative dynamics of innovation and fostering the digital transition of the economy, public administration, society and inland territories (CMF, 2021).

The consortium, which submitted the application to create DIH4Sm@rtRegions, consists of 12 entities and includes the municipalities of Fundão and Bragança, the Polytechnic Institutes of Viana do Castelo, Bragança, Guarda and Castelo Branco, the collaborative laboratories "Research Mountains and Forestwise", the clusters of Mineral Resources and InovCluster, Brigantia Ecopark and AQUAVALOR - Centre for the Enhancement and Transfer of Water Technology. This results from a clear vision of the strategy to be implemented in terms of investing investment, keeping capital and people in rural areas, making this territory increasingly competitive, through a collaborative network that aims at improving the quality of life of the populations.

Fundão is also present in two other consortia that aim to create DIHs in distinct themes. The first one, through ADXTUR - Agency for the Touristic Development of Schist Villages, aims at creating a hub in digital fabrication, stating the importance of Fab Labs to develop, test and introduce new digital solutions in the economy, institutions and society (PT.DIGMAKING.IH). The second one, through the Plant Biotechnology Centre of Beira Interior, aims at creating a hub to accelerate the transition to sustainable agriculture models, with a focus on small and medium agricultural productions (EDIH-F4S).

In this process, the active participation of the Municipality of Fundão, together with the collaboration in the two hubs mentioned above, follows the local strategy of innovation and investment, with special focus on digital. This process comes as a response to the challenge launched by the European Union and the Portuguese State for the creation of the DIH network, and it is a way to pursue the objectives inscribed in the [Digital Europe Programme](#) and in the [Action Plan for Digital Transition](#), as well as in the Strategic Vision for the Economic Recovery Plan for Portugal 2020-2030, a document that served as the basis for the Recovery and Resilience Plan (RRP). It was also signalled as an anchor project regarding digital innovation clusters by the [Expand Programme](#).

2.4. Des Agro 4.0 Project

The [Des Agro 4.0](#) project, co-financed through the ERDF programme and promoted by [DOLMEN](#), [RUDE](#), [UTAD](#) and [IPCB](#), aims to empower Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) of the agro-food and agro-industrial sector of Douro Verde and Cova da Beira, with skills and knowledge that make them able to adopt and incorporate into their activity, intelligent business models. These must necessarily be based and supported on the so-called Internet of Things (IoT) or, in general, in the concept "Industry 4.0", namely those that represent a support for decision-making. The implementation of Des Agro 4.0 project aims to fill the gaps identified in the sector, by combating the lack of knowledge of SMEs about technologies applicable to their business and their economic dimension, while promoting the adoption and implementation of advanced technology in the agri-food and agro-industrial sector.

3. Position of the Multi-Actor Platform

3.1. Identified needs

The first joint work with MAP members consisted in identifying the main needs and/or challenges related to digitalisation, in the Fundão region, highlighting:

- **Connectivity** in agriculture (having connectivity in the field).
- **Transfer of existing technology.**
- Lack of **digital skills** (strengthening through capacity building and rejuvenation policies in agriculture).
- Unadjusted **financing models.**
- Technologies/equipment with **language adapted to** the end user.
- Limitation linked to **regulation** (e.g. use of drones).
- Role of digitisation as a **communication tool.**
- Making **data** easier to **use.**
- Lack of **manpower.**
- **Business dynamism**, jobs, connecting the rural areas to urban centres.

In parallel, certain tools and messages were identified to address the identified needs, such as:

- **Empowering** the user of digitalisation in agriculture (digital tools).
- Knowing how to communicate **technological developments.**
- Greater **involvement of** local communities.
- **Clarity of the objectives of** rural areas.
- Challenges of **governance** and policy orientation.
- **Advanced digitalisation** in the forestry sector.
- Relevant role of **CoLabs** in engaging digitalisation strategy in rural areas.
- Digitalisation as a **tool to bring** people **closer to** the territory.

Figure 1 - First Meeting with MAP RURAL_PT members

1ª reunião | MAP RURAL_PT | 3º Ciclo
A digitalização nas zonas rurais

Figure 2 - Results of the group dynamics with MAP RURAL_PT members | Needs

3.2. Existing interventions and actions

Table 1 - Examples of actions taken by local actors

Agrotech IoT Centre

Its objectives are: i) promote the integration of IoT solutions in the economy, especially in rural-based activities; ii) attract new entrepreneurs and investors, reinforcing the connection to universities and polytechnics; iii) strengthen the conditions to host teams to develop products and solutions based on technological processes; iv) consolidate an ecosystem of IoT technology development and validation that serves as an interface between research and the market; v) unblock financial constraints for the development of entrepreneurial initiatives based on IoT technology; vi) disseminate best practices in the development and application of IoT in rural-based businesses; vii) create and boost a wide networking network.

Website: <https://movetofundao.pt/iot-open-lab/#1572633639546-136fdb2-e597>

FAB LAB Schist Villages

It is a space for low-cost creation and experimentation, where there are no limits to creativity. This laboratory was the first to be born in the region of Fundão, in which the City Hall is the main promoter, betting on a strategy of innovation and entrepreneurship. This space provides advanced technology that is available to the common citizen to find the best way to materialise the projects. The idea is to provide help in finding the most appropriate solutions for those who seek new creative and entrepreneurial paths.

Website: <https://movetofundao.pt/fab-lab-aldeias-do-xisto/>

Incubator “A Praça”

It consists of a set of spaces and services made available by the Municipality of Fundão to give way to new business initiatives. The Incubator is duly accredited to provide services in the scope of Vale Incubação and recognised before the National Incubator Network. Its main objective is to create networks for territorial cooperation, and to spread innovative logics, technological hosting, and innovative entrepreneurship.

Website: <https://movetofundao.pt/incubacao-e-aceleracao/>

EU SOU DIGITAL - Digital training programme for adults

This programme aims to eradicate the digital illiteracy of one million adults in Portugal, through a national network of thousands of volunteers and 1,500 spaces spread across the country. It aims to promote digital literacy, teaching adults who have never used the Internet to do so. Fundão was in the spotlight at the launch of the programme EU SOU DIGITAL - Programa de Capacitação Digital de Adultos, which took place on 06 July 2021.

Website: <https://www.eusoudigital.pt/>

Agricultural Innovation Fair

The first edition of this event was held this year, 2022, in the region of Fundão. It was attended by experts, members of academia, technology companies and strategic decision-makers in the sphere of local and agricultural development policies, with a programme that included conferences, lectures, round tables, debate panels, networking moments and, demonstration actions of innovative technologies applicable to the development of a smarter agriculture.

Website: <http://www.movetofundao.pt/fiafundao/>

AgroTech Challenge

This is an initiative of the Municipality of Fundão, CCILB - Câmara do Comércio e Indústria Luso-Brasileira, CIEBI - Centro de Inovação Empresarial da Beira Interior, VeraTech Company and the Brazilian Embassy in Portugal. It aims to promote the development of integrated and customised solutions for agriculture, from the presentation of answers to 4 challenges: 1) development of agronomic indexes based on aerial images; 2) publication of agricultural activities in block chain; 3) frost forecasting using artificial intelligence; 4) almond counting using Machine Vision.

Website: <https://movetofundao.pt/agrochallenge/>

3.3. Recommendations from the MAP

3.3.1. Recommendations for future rural policies

One of the challenges issued to the MAP members was to identify recommended policy interventions for the Fundão region to be implemented at local, regional and/or national level. The results for this exercise were as follows:

- **Local level:**
 - Strengthening the digital skills of farmers and stakeholders in the agricultural sector.
 - Creation of demonstration centres.
 - Support for the setting-up of young farmers.
 - Promotion of automation and robotisation.
 - Support for the installation of equipment to improve the mobile network in rural areas.
 - Support for the development of integrated farm management systems.
- **Regional level:**
 - Promoting the provision of services and technical assistance in Precision Farming - Regulation, eligibility and SPCAP funding, through capacity building actions for Producer Organisations.
 - Development and implementation of warning networks (phytosanitary, irrigation) with data sharing between public administration and private entities.
 - Support for investment in collective solutions, with the aim of making the technology needed for small farmers to become more "digital" available in an affordable and effective way.
 - Promoting more programmes for the settlement of skilled migrants.
- **National level:**
 - Development of national policies and European funding to promote connectivity in non-urban areas.
 - Availability of public support/investment to stimulate new Operational Groups.
 - Creation of a Competence Centre linked to Digitalisation.
 - Support in the use of monitoring and impact measurement tools for the different production systems.
 - Data HUB/Data Space to support the development of new solutions - EU policy and funding.
 - Within SPCAP, enable the wider use of support for the purchase of services as opposed to equipment – Regulate.
 - Development of a joint platform that aggregates all relevant geographic-based information for the digitisation of agriculture (data collection and sharing).
 - Creation of a governance and protection model for data provided by farmers.
 - Promote the mandatory sharing of relevant data for digitisation under CAP support.

3.3.2. Recommendations for future research agendas

The last challenge launched to the MAP members was to identify the main gaps in knowledge and future research, for the Fundão region.

This exercise focused mainly on the agricultural activity in the region.

At the level of **knowledge gaps**, the following outputs were obtained:

- New predictive models for crop, climate, pests and diseases based on in situ environmental and earth observation data.
- Development of irrigation decision support models based on Earth observation data.
- Automation of harvesting.
- Mechanisms for interoperability between equipment.
- Intelligent spraying mechanisms.
- Automatic detection of pests and diseases.
- Establishment of correlations between the use of production factors and crops, to optimise the use of resources.
- Advanced training in the areas of IoT and precision agriculture, so that local producers can take advantage of the existing facilities available to them.

In terms of **research priorities** for the Fundão region, the following stands out:

- Irrigation efficiency.
- Fertiliser use efficiency.
- Efficiency in the use of phytosanitary treatments.
- Early detection of pests and diseases.
- Precision Treatments.
- Applied research into the reduction of energy and water consumption (irrigated or own) in all existing crops in the municipality of Fundão.

Conclusions

The MAP RURAL_PT focused on the Fundão region because this municipality has been standing out, over the last years, for the implementation of a local innovation and investment strategy, with special focus on digital. All work developed with local actors, from policy, science and society, allowed to identify the main needs of the region, in terms of digitalisation, as well as the main actions already implemented on the field and the main knowledge gaps.

The whole document has a greater focus on agriculture, mainly due to the sector of action of the different local actors involved in the MAP. However, the topic of digitalisation has the particularity of being transversal to all sectors, to the extent that some depend on others, as is the case of connectivity, the strengthening of skills in general, and the strengthening of knowledge transfer.

MAP members were challenged to identify the main recommendations for the digital transition at local, regional and national level, and the following results were produced: (i) strengthen digital skills of the different local actors; (ii) create demonstration centres/exploits; (iii) promote programmes to support the settlement of qualified labour; (iv) increase connectivity in non-urbanised areas; (v) support for the development of integrated agricultural management systems; (vi) develop national policies and European funding to support local actors for the new digital Era; (vii) promote data sharing between the different local actors, whether public or private sector.

In terms of recommendations for future research agendas, it is important to highlight the concern of local actors about knowledge gaps that still exist in the domains of precision agriculture and Internet of Things. However, it is common knowledge that the adoption of digital technologies in agriculture is something progressive and dynamic in farms and it depends on different variables such as physical size, technical capacity, the existence of connectivity, among others. On the other hand, the diversity of technologies and the speed at which new technological solutions emerge make this transformation more complex, so there is not yet a "standard" solution for all.

As digitalisation is a dynamic and constantly evolving concept, it was important to maintain joint work with local actors over time. This collaboration would be aimed at updating and monitoring the measures already implemented and the inclusion of new strategies, always in line with the Portuguese Government's vision in this area, reinforcing the dynamism of priorities and concerns of the economy and society.

Like the measures, the follow-up and monitoring indicators may also evolve, through the inclusion of new concepts or redefinition of priorities at regional level, as instruments for gauging the proposed objectives and established goals. It is intended that the Municipality of Fundão continues with the excellent work done so far, as a differentiating and innovative example, standing out for being the most digital rural area in Portugal.

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank all the MAP Members who promptly responded to all the proposed challenges throughout this third cycle of the MAP RURAL_PT.

This third cycle coincided with the period of reformulations and discussions at the level of territorial development policies and with the summer holiday period, which hampered the involvement and engagement of the different sector agents throughout the cycle. However, it is important to highlight the quality and rationale put forward by MAP members in all the proposed challenges, culminating in this Position Paper, which clearly reflects the perspectives of those on the field and those who fight daily for the municipality of Fundão to gain a prominent place on the innovation world map.

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Annex 1 Methodology used by the MAP

This third and last MAP cycle will no longer have a regional scope, but a local one, as it will focus on a specific district of the Centro region of Portugal, Fundão. Over the past few years, Fundão has been investing in a strategy to attract investment, create jobs and foster innovation with the aim of promoting the diversification of the local economy and a socio-economic development adapted to the dynamics of the current economy marked by globalisation and digitalisation.

In 2013, the Fundão Innovation Plan was implemented, whose objective was to create an ecosystem that would promote the attraction of local investment, while creating incentives for retaining the active population, creating more and better jobs and acquiring new markets, products, and services, contributing to greater competitiveness and attraction of the territory. Apart from promoting the traditional business sectors of this territory, there was a strong investment in new sectors and activities linked to digitalisation, namely software development services, robotics, and technology-based research centres.

It is important to highlight that Fundão has a creative ecosystem of open innovation with a set of skills and services that include: areas for receiving companies; spaces for teamwork and incubation; a Fab Lab integrated and certified by the global network; a Business and Services Centre with technical and safety standards recognised by the sector and an Advanced Training Centre.

Table - Summary of the key information about the MAP

Key data	Description
Name and location of the MAP (country and region)	MAP RURAL_EN (Fundão Centro Region Portugal)
Composition of the MAP	20 MAP Members 6 policy 8 science 6 society
Name of Facilitator	Pedro Santos
Name of Monitor	Marta Mendes
Valid period	2021-2023

Working methods and planned activities for the 3rd MAP cycle

Working methods

1. Sharing of support documents for the development of the third cycle
2. Periodic communication with MAP Members with the aim of maintaining their involvement and interaction in the MAP
3. 1st Meeting | Face-to-face group discussion
4. 2nd Meeting | Individual reflection
5. Validation of the Position Paper with MAP members

Planned activities for the 3rd MAP cycle

- *Creation of the MAP working group*

An invitation email was sent to the main local agents of the Fundão territory to create a new group of MAP members, due to the significant loss of members in the previous cycles. This email aimed to inform about the SHERPA project, its main objectives, as well as the topic to be discussed in this cycle. Each member, after accepting the invitation, sent to us the consent form, duly filled.

- *Sharing of documents supporting the development of the cycle*

The cycle's work plan started when all the documents that support MAP development was shared with the MAP Members, namely the SHERPA Discussion Paper, as well as other bibliography essential for understanding the objectives of this cycle. All these documents have been translated in Portuguese and sent by email.

- *1st Meeting | Face-to-face group discussion*

Organisation of a group meeting, in an exclusively face-to-face format, with the aim of sharing knowledge, experiences and perspectives of the different local agents, linked to policy, science and society. This meeting have been organised in group dynamics sessions and sharing of outputs in plenary session, with the objective of answering all the objectives foreseen for this cycle. Thus, below some topics of the draft agenda that were shared with participants:

- ✓ SHERPA Discussion Paper: Summary & Main goal
- ✓ SHERPA Discussion Paper: Background
- ✓ Brief explanation of the key objectives of digitisation in rural areas
- ✓ Group dynamic | Klaxoon platform: What are the needs of the area covered by the MAP in relation to (topic)?

- *2nd Meeting | individual reflection*

To give continuity to the work developed by the MAP Members in the first meeting, and once the main needs of the Fundão region have been identified, the Facilitator and the moderator considered that it would be more assertive to answer the following three questions if the members carried out an individual reflection. In this sense, a guiding document was prepared so that the members could carry out the proposed exercises. The document was structured as follows:

- ✓ Main results of the 1st MAP meeting - Identification of needs
- ✓ 1st exercise to answer the following questions - "Examples of policy interventions already in place, at the level of digitalisation, in the region of Fundão? "; "Examples of actions undertaken by local actors addressing these needs implemented in Fundão? "
- ✓ 2nd exercise "What policy interventions are recommended by MAP members to be implemented at local, regional and/or national level, and how can the EU support these interventions? "
- ✓ 3rd exercise "What are the knowledge gaps, and what are the research priorities for this region, at the level of digitisation?"

EXERCÍCIO 1

Exemplos de intervenções políticas já em curso, ao nível de digitalização, no âmbito do Fundo?

post-it

Exemplos de ações empreendidas pelos atores locais que abordam estas necessidades implementadas no Fundo?

post-it

EXERCÍCIO 2

Que intervenções políticas são recomendadas pelos membros de TRGP para serem implementadas a nível local, regional e/ou nacional, e como pode a UE apoiar estas intervenções?

LOCAL

REGIONAL

NACIONAL

INSTRUMENTOS DE MEDIDAS

post-it

post-it

post-it

EXERCÍCIO 3

Quais são as lacunas de conhecimento, e que nova investigação é necessária?

LACUNAS DE CONHECIMENTO

post-it

PRIORIDADES DE INVESTIGAÇÃO

post-it

Figure - Exercises developed by the MAP Members in individual reflection

- *Validation of the MAP Position Paper*

After the face-to-face meeting and individual reflection, all collected inputs have been analysed and worked on to result in the MAP RURAL_EN Position Paper. This document, written in English, was translated into Portuguese, and sent by email to MAP Members for final validation. Afterwards it has been sent to the SHERPA project.

- *Sharing the SHERPA Position Paper*

Once the SHERPA Position Paper is finalised, it is shared by email with all MAP members.

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